

ABRomics web Application

Progress of the β version release

Julie Lao, Romain Dallet, Kenzo-Hugo Hillion, Alix de Thoisy, Pierre Marin &
Fabien Mareuil

Dashboard (work in progress)

 ABRomics
ANTIBIORESISTANCE

ABROMICS DATABASE DASHBOARD [MY ACCOUNT](#)

Projects

[CREATE NEW PROJECT](#)

Name	Description	Actions
Escherichia coli - 06/2023	Escherichia coli collected in 06/2023 from X laboratory	
Klebsiella pneumoniae - 01-03/2023	Klebsiella pneumoniae for the 1st trimester	
Klebsiella aerogenes - KA campain	Klebsiella aerogenes data from te KA campain	
Salmonella enterica - 2022	Salmonella enterica collected in 2022 from Y laboratory	

Upload (work in progress)

Upload Data

Upload metadata file

Choose a metadata file (.xlsx)

2022-07-18_ABRomics_GENOMIC-WGS_v0.1.3_small_example.xlsx (95.9 kB)

Upload raw read files

Choose a data file (.fastq)

r2_reverse.fastq (88 B)

r1_forward.fastq (54 B)

2 files (142 B in total)

SUBMIT DATA

Experiment

Row number	Sample	Metadata file
1	1	1
2	2	1
3	3	1
1	4	7
2	5	7
3	6	7